

IMPROVING THE COST MANAGEMENT MECHANISM IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY LOGISTIC CHAINS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6574487>

Mirsodiqov Abdulla Tursunalievich

Basic doctoral student of Fergana State University

Abstract: *The article deals with the issues of improving the cost management mechanisms in the supply chains of the construction industry. The activities of foreign and domestic scientists, reflecting the results of various studies, and some related concepts, as well as the author's definitions. For the activities of a large construction company, a multifactorial model was chosen based on the factors influencing the formation of costs in the supply chains of the construction industry. Based on the indicators for 2014-2021, a multifactorial model of non-linear relationships was developed, and on the basis of this model, forecast indicators for the formation of costs in supply chains for the medium term were determined. In the course of the study, a complex organizational and economic mechanism for managing the logistics business processes of a construction cluster was developed, which expands the possibilities for improving the efficiency of the process of managing the movement of material and information flows in logistics chains in the activities of regional construction clusters.*

Keywords: *construction industry, logistics, capital construction, building complexes, logistics chains, management, logistics costs, construction cluster.*

Introduction

As part of the economy, the construction industry is one of the fastest growing sectors. It addresses key reproductive and economic issues related to the reproductive aspect of the economy and housing construction. Especially in recent years, the construction industry has become one of the fastest growing sectors of the economy. However, in the course of the development of the industry, there was a certain spread of economic ties between all participants in the construction complexes.

The introduction of approaches to the formation of logistics chains in the management of the capital construction process, taking into account the existing economic and organizational potential, is of great importance at the current stage of development of the industry. This is due to the acceleration of construction production, the use of new materials and construction technologies, expanding the level of horizontal economic ties between construction companies, increasing the intensity of economic flows in construction and the necessary level of integration of industries. In this context, the importance of logistical coordination of material, information and financial flows, ensuring the agreed activities during the construction, procurement, transportation, delivery and preparation of production and technological configurations for the facilities under construction and at the site is growing.

Research methodology

In the study, cost management in the logistics chains of the construction industry has been extensively studied theoretically on the basis of monographic research. Based on official statistics, using the Eviews10 analysis program, an econometric model was identified based on time series of logistics costs and factors influencing it in the construction sector, which is the main indicator, assessed trends in key parameters and forecast indicators for the short term.

Scientific abstraction, correlation-regression analysis, analysis and synthesis methods were used as research methodology in the research process.

Analysis and results

The analysis of changes in the framework of structural changes in the country shows that the main factors in ensuring economic growth at the macroeconomic level are the support of construction companies, the formation of logistics chains in the construction industry, as well as the establishment of a new, modern and effective construction management system. taken.

A multifactor analysis of the changes in the costs of the logistics chain in the construction industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan under the influence of the main factor influencing the indicator, which is an endogenous factor.

In the construction sector, the following indicators were selected based on the findings of industry experts as indicators of the factor influencing the logistics chain costs as the peak of the production function, ie the outcome factor:

X1 - volume of construction work performed;

X2 - management costs in the logistics chain;

X3 is the share of its logistics systems in the total chain;

Each influencing exogenous factor is, by its very nature, a motive for logistics chain costs in the construction industry. For example, if the total volume of construction work determines the load of the logistics system required for the organization of activities, management costs reflect the ability to optimize the operation of the logistics chain, the share of their logistics systems in the overall chain.

Modeling of logistics costs in the enterprises of the logistics chain operating in the construction industry of the country can be carried out using models such as trends, tendencies and time series, occurring in the market of specific services. In the course of the study, the analysis of trends in the costs of the logistics chain and some indicators affecting its formation in 2014-2021 at a construction and installation company operating in Fergana region (Table 1).

Indicators such as the volume of construction work performed (x_1), the volume of management costs in the logistics chain (x_2) and the share of their logistics systems in

the total chain (x3) were selected as exogenous factors influencing the volume of logistics chain costs (Y) selected as a final factor in the econometric model.

Table 1 Indicators of the cost of logistics chain costs in construction and installation companies and the factors influencing its change (billion soums)

Years	Logistics chain costs, mln. sum (Y)	Volume of construction works performed, mln. sum (X1)	Management costs in the logistics chain, million soums (X2)	Share of own logistics systems in the total chain,% (X3)
2014	53639,1	487628,4	64952,1	19,6
2015	63161,6	619231,8	83441,5	19,6
2016	72647,8	698536,5	85500,9	23,4
2017	76331,8	763317,9	107337,8	25,3
2018	99376,5	1057197,3	135786,4	63,2
2019	77528,5	861427,9	103759,0	66,7
2020	73728,1	801392,2	127902,2	69,5
2021	82208,7	838714,3	109328,1	68,8

When considering the nature of endogenous factors and exogenous factors, the volume of construction work, management costs in the logistics chain and factors that have a significant impact on the share of their logistics systems in the overall chain are considered in the form of Cobb-Douglas production model. will have a link that is close to the model. Based on the combination of key endogenous and exogenous factors, in order to identify trends in the volume of costs of the logistics chain in "Yangi Avlod Qurilish Invest" LLC, the above time series data were analyzed using the program EViews10.

The level of double correlation between the costs of the logistics chain and the factors influencing it in the activities of "Yangi Avlod Qurilish Invest" LLC was studied on the basis of correlation analysis. The correlation analysis satisfies the required condition that the density of the relationship between the resulting factor and the influencing factors is $ryx1 = 0.9774$, $ryx2 = 0.8618$, and $ryx3 = 0.8618$. In all three correlations, the double correlation coefficient indicates a close correlation, indicating that the factors influencing the outcome factor were selected correctly.

Table 2 Yangi Avlod Qurilish Invest LLC Correlation of selected factor ²⁵

	<i>y</i>	<i>x1</i>	<i>x2</i>	<i>x3</i>
<i>y</i>	1			
<i>x1</i>	0,977436	1		
<i>x2</i>	0,861774	0,908816	1	
<i>x3</i>	0,66228	0,769093	0,782153	1

In the table above, we can define the basic trend model in the form of a linear logarithmic relationship because the unit of measurement of the resultant and influencing factor indices is not the same, i.e., the factor indices are not homogeneous. To do this, all factor indices are reduced to natural logarithmic indices (Table 3).

Table 3

Logarithmic value of the volume of costs in the logistics chain and the factors influencing its change in the activities of "Yangi Avlod Qurilish Invest" LLC ²⁶

<i>t</i>	<i>LnY</i>	<i>LnX₁</i>	<i>LnX₂</i>	<i>LnX₃</i>
2014	10,89	13,10	11,08	2,98
2015	11,05	13,34	11,33	2,98
2016	11,19	13,46	11,36	3,15
2017	11,24	13,55	11,58	3,23
2018	11,51	13,87	11,82	4,15
2019	11,26	13,67	11,55	4,20
2020	11,21	13,59	11,76	4,24
2021	11,32	13,64	11,60	4,23

The parameters identified in the regression analysis performed using the Eviews10 software package, as well as the importance of the model, were assessed using key evaluation indicators calculated by the program.

From the results of the regression analysis, a logarithmic model of the trend is formed by separating the coefficients of the regression model for the situation under consideration.

The enterprises obtained for analysis using the multifactor econometric model were expressed in the short term under the influence of economic and management factors of the volume of logistics chain costs, ie the values of change in 2022-2024 on the basis of Table 4.

Table 4 Forecasts of the volume of costs and management performance of logistics chains in "Yangi Avlod Qurilish Invest" LLC in 2022-2024 ²⁷

²⁵ Developed by the author based on Microsoft Excel

²⁶ Developed on the basis of author's calculations.

Years	Logistics chain costs, mln. sum (Y)	Volume of construction works performed, mln. sum (X1)	Management costs in the logistics chain, million soums (X2)	Share of own logistics systems in the total chain,% (X3)
2022	89982,1	988303,5	135259,5	85,3
2023	93729,4	1037719,6	142594,7	94,4
2024	97117,6	1087135,8	149929,9	100,0

Based on the regression coefficient of the variables in the multifactor model, which represents the change in the volume of logistics chain costs in the construction enterprise obtained for analysis, we can assess the degree of their impact on the outcome factor. In particular, the volume of construction work performed at Yangi Avlod Qurilish Invest LLC and the increase in the share of its logistics systems in the overall chain are directly related to changes in the outcome factor, the volume of management costs in the logistics chain and the overall impact of random factors.

When using the proposed multi-factor model in the process of managing the formation of costs in the logistics chain in the construction company, it is necessary to take into account the impact of each influencing factor on the outcome factor. At the same time, Yangi Avlod Qurilish Invest LLC will be able to focus on increasing the share of its logistics systems in the logistics chain and management costs. The use of identified trends allows optimizing the efficiency per unit of output by correctly allocating the amount of resources involved in the organization of the process of cost management in the logistics chain of enterprises.

Trend models identified on the basis of multifactor correlation allow predicting the change in costs in the logistics chains of enterprises in the future in the future under the influence of selected factors, taking into account errors within a certain limit.

The activities of the coordinating logistics team should be based on the need to achieve the following objectives:

1. Formation of stable logistics relations between cluster participants, creation of conditions for optimization of logistics processes.

2. Improving the socio-economic performance of construction projects based on the expansion of economic ties between construction companies and logistics infrastructure enterprises.

3. Attracting new participants to the regional construction clusters, ensuring the development of contractors in the form of specialized and innovative enterprises based on the optimization of the system of external integration relations not only within the cluster, but also outside the cluster

Conclusions and suggestions

²⁷ Developed by the author.

Based on the above tasks and practical results, the following suggestions and recommendations were made:

- Multi-factor models based on the factors influencing the formation of costs in the logistics chain of the construction industry were developed on the basis of selected performance indicators of large construction enterprises for 2014-2021. Based on the relationship between factors such as the volume of construction work performed, management costs in the logistics chain, and the share of their logistics systems in the total chain, which affect the multifactor models developed, the cost of selected logistics chains is 3 large constructions. Directions for optimizing the level of performance factor in enterprises were identified.

- On the basis of theoretical, methodological and practical research, the development of enterprises operating in the construction industry on the basis of clusters in the form of territorial horizontal, vertical or mixed management structures was assessed as more effective than existing separate activities. It was found that the logistics chains in the organization of construction clusters operate in the form of a structure that creates the necessary conditions for the main activity, and the organization of their activities in proportion to the capacity of the focus enterprise has a positive impact on the final results of the cluster participants

REFERENCES:

1. Полещук, И.И. Идентификация и планирование логистических издержек: методологический аспект / И.И. Полещук // Государственное регулирование экономики и повышение эффективности деятельности субъектов хозяйствования: сб. науч. ст. / Акад. упр. при Президенте Респ. Беларусь; редкол.: С.А. Пелих [и др.]. – Минск, 2017. – С. 122–126.

2. Mirzaev, A. T. (2020). Assessment of cluster formation in management of recreational activity. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 04 (84), 605-610. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2020.04.84.101>

3. Mirzaev, A.T (2018) "The level of use of tourist attractions in the regions and the factors affecting them," *Economics and Innovative Technologies: Vol. 2018: No.3, Article 19*. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/iqtisodiyot/vol2018/iss3/19>

4. Мирзаев А.Т. Совершенствование интегральной оценки механизма рекреационно-туристических объектов // Бюллетень науки и практики. 2019. Т. 5. №2. С. 127-134. <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/39/17>

5. Мирзаев А.Т. Оценка использования рекреационных возможностей на рынке туристических услуг // Региональная экономика: теория и практика. – 2019. – Т. 17, № 5. – С. 990 – 1002. <https://doi.org/10.24891/re.17.5.990>.

6. Mirzaev A. T. Evaluation of innovation capacity resource components in effective management of recreational clusters on the basis of econometric analysis //

EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD). – 2020. – pp.131-137. <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra4790>.

7. Мирзаев А. Т. Совершенствование системы электронного бронирования как часть цифрования управленческой деятельности туристско-рекреационных предприятий // Бюллетень науки и практики. 2020.Т.6.№8. С.165-172. <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/57/14>

8. Мирзаев А. Т. Туристик-рекреация объектлари кластерларини шакллантириш механизмларини баҳолаш // Иқтисодиёт ва таълим [Текст]. 2018. №6. 207-213 б.

9. Mirzaev A.T. Туристик-рекреация кластерларини бошқаришда инновацион салоҳиятнинг ресурс компонентини баҳолаш услубиёти “Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar” ilmiy elektron jurnali. № 4, iyul-avgust, 2020 yil. 390-401 б.